

PATHOGENIC DIVERSITY IN *Ascochyta rabiei* IN CHICKPEA (*Cicer arietinum* L.) IN THE WESTERN OF ALGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Ascochyta rabiei is a fungus agent responsible for the anthracnose of the chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) causing serious disease in Algeria and all over the world. Ten isolates of *A. rabiei* were harvested in five regions in western Algeria. Isolates used in this study are characterised pathogenically after their inoculations on thirteen chickpea lines including seven introduced lines, and six local lines. The artificial inoculations were carried out by spraying an inoculum (5.10^5 spores/ml) on fifteen (15) days aged seedlings. The results obtained show the existence of a pathogenic variability of this agent. Regarding the evaluation of the aggressiveness of the studied isolates, it seems that the isolate MSC2 is particularly aggressive with respect to all inoculated lines, followed by SB2 and REL1, five isolates are moderately aggressive (MSC1, SB1, SB3, MOS2 and REL2), two are non-aggressive isolates (AT1 and MOS1). The aggressivity study revealed three levels of aggressiveness: highly aggressive isolates, moderately aggressive isolates and non-aggressive isolates. For the evaluation of the reaction of tested chickpea lines, the results obtained allowed us to classify the tested lines in three categories. Through this study, we believe that pathogenic variability is necessary for an approach to molecular characterisation.

KEYWORDS:

Ascochyta rabiei, *Cicer arietinum* L., Pathogenicity, Aggressivity, Algeria

INTRODUCTION

Food legumes in Algeria have always been third in terms of the area, after cereals and fodder. Their area is of the order of 90 thousand hectares representing 0.21% of the total agricultural area in 2014. The most cultivated species are in order: beans, chickpeas, dry peas, lentils and dried beans [1-2].

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.), one of the most important grain legumes in Algeria, ranks second after bean fever. Most of the cultivated area of this spe-

cies is concentrated in the west of the country, particularly in Tlemcen and Ain-Temouchent regions [1].

In Algeria, despite the sharp increase in the area planted to chickpea, yields remained very low. They hardly exceed eight quintals per hectare. This low production is due to an overall rainfall deficit, and unevenly distributed over time and space. In addition to this, poor soil cultivation, a proliferation of weeds, poor seed conditions and phytosanitary problems are added. It is above all the susceptibility to diseases where anthracnose, foliar disease caused by a fungus *Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Which remains the most formidable disease [3]. One of the greatest biotic stresses reducing potential yields in chickpea is ascochyta blight caused by *Ascochyta rabiei* Pass. (Labr.) (Teleomorph, *Didymella rabiei* v. Arx. syn. *Mycosphaerella rabiei* Kovachevski) [4]. The use of resistant chickpea cultivars is the most effective and economical management strategy for ascochyta blight [5-6]. The concentration of the inoculum is one of the important factors influencing the severity and epidemiology of plant diseases. [7]. Studies conducted in Algeria on the pathogenicity of the parasite show a great variability on these traits [1-7-8]. Our research work addresses the problem of a fungal disease in Algeria that is chickpea anthracnose. Our goal is to study pathogenic variability. Isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei* against a range of different chickpea lines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material. Origin of lines. During the 2015-2016 crop year, ten (10) plots were prospected in five regions in western Algeria that was favourable for growing chickpeas (Mascara, Sidi Bel-Abbes, Ain Temouchent, Mostaganem and Relizane) (Figure 1).

The plant material consists of a set of lines used by many researchers working on chickpea anthracnose in the study of the pathogenicity of *A. rabiei* isolates. We used thirteen (13) varieties provided by INRAA / URO of Sidi Bel Abbes. Six (06) are local and seven (07) introduced (Table 1).

FIGURE 1
Map of five surveyed regions and collecting samples of chickpeas

TABLE 1
Differential chickpea lines and their origin

Chickpea Lines	Type	Origin
ILC 482	Kabuli	ICARDA*
F 97-657	Kabuli	ICARDA
ILC 3279	Kabuli	ICARDA
ILC 263	Kabuli	ICARDA
F 03-19C	Kabuli	ICARDA
Flip 05-69C	Kabuli	ICARDA
INRA 199	Desi	INRA**
F 10-25	Kabuli	Local
F 10-5/11	Kabuli	Local
Col 08	Kabuli	Local
GP 10	Kabuli	Local
Col 25/24	Kabuli	Local
F482	Kabuli	Local

* International Centre for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas, Aleppo, Syria.

**INRA: National Institute of Agronomic Research, Versailles, France.

Fungal material. Isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei*.

The isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei* used in this study were obtained by isolation from stalk samples, stems and chickpea pods with symptoms of anthracnose. Ten (10) isolates were used in this test (Table 2).

Isolation and purification of cultures. The isolates were conserved in Petri dishes contained CSMDA medium (Chickpea Seed Meal Dextrose Agar) [10]. The isolates were maintained on CSMDA medium at 20±2°C [11].

Inoculum preparation. The seeds of the lines used are immersed in a solution containing 2% sodium hypochlorite for 3 minutes. They are rinsed 3 times with distilled water of one seed per pot (10 x 6 cm) containing a substrate of peat and river sand (1/1,

v / v). The sand is previously disinfected by the Bergerac method. The plants are carefully watered, 1 day on 2, with tap water.

Inoculation of plants. A spore suspension of ten isolate was prepared from 15-day-old cultures as described above. The suspension was filtered through two layers of muslin cloth and spore concentration was determined with a haematocytometer and adjusted to $5 \cdot 10^5$ spores/ml with sterile distilled water. Tween 80 was added to the spore suspension as a surfactant agent for sticking the spore to leaves of chickpea plants. Inoculation was done on 15-day-old plants. The pots are first put in closed plastic containers. After that, they are transferred to a greenhouse and sprayed daily with sterile distilled water until the appearance of symptoms.

TABLE 2
Geographical origin and designation of *A. rabiei* isolates in western Algeria

Isolates	Geographical origins	Sites	Dates of isolation	Isolation organs
MSC1	Mascara	Maoussa	November 2015	Pod
MSC2	Mascara	Tighennif	December 2015	Pod
AT1	Ain Temouchent	Hassi El Ghalla	November 2016	Pod
SB1	Sidi Bel Abbes	Tassala	September 2015	Stem
SB2	Sidi Bel Abbes	Sidi Lahsen	October 2015	Stem
SB3	Sidi Bel Abbes	Attouche	October 2015	Pod
MOS1	Mostaganem	Sidi Ali	September 2016	Pod
MOS2	Mostaganem	Sidi Lakhdar	September 2016	Stem
REL1	Relizane	Mendes	October 2016	Stem
REL2	Relizane	Yellel	October 2016	Stem

Rating scale. The severity of the disease is noted from 1 to 9, according to the scale of [12]. Which is based on the intensity of the symptoms, 21 days after inoculation presents itself as follows:

- 1 = No infection;
- 2 = Highly resistant (lesions on 1–5% of the plant);
- 3 = Resistant (lesions on 6–10%);
- 4 = Moderately resistant (lesions on 11–15%);
- 5 = Intermediate (lesions on 16–40%);
- 6 = Moderately susceptible (lesions on 41–50%);
- 7 = Susceptible (lesions on 51–75%);
- 8 = Highly susceptible (lesions on 76–100%);
- 9 = Highly susceptible, plant killed.

The chickpea lines rated 1.0 to 4.9 were considered resistant and those rated 5.0 to 9.0 were considered susceptible [13]. The classification of *Ascochyta rabiei* isolates is based on degree intervals of aggressiveness [10];

- A. 1 - 3.9 : Moderately aggressive isolate;
- B. 4 - 5.9 : Non-aggressive isolate;
- C. 6 - 9 : Highly aggressive isolate;

The intervals below were used to know the susceptible, tolerant and resistant varieties [10];

- 1- Resistant variety (R) : 1-3.9 ;
- 2- Tolerant variety (T) : 4-5.9 ;
- 3- Sensitive variety (S) : 6-7.9 ;
- 4- Variety very sensitive (VS) : 8-9 ;

The degree of attack is evaluated by an average attack index: (Eq. 1)

This coefficient makes it possible to assess the attack quantitatively and to express the level of sensitivity or resistance of the plant.

Statistical analysis. The variances (σ^2), averages and standard deviation (SD) of various repetitions were calculated and analysed by the software of statistics (STAT BOX 6.0.4. GRIMMERSOFT) and the device used are the unifactorial total randomisation (one studied factor) by the Newman and Keuls test ($P_{0.05}$ and $P_{0.01}$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Study of the pathogenicity of *Ascochyta rabiei*. Inoculation on a susceptible chickpea lines ILC 263. The inoculation of the ILC 263 line with the ten (10) isolates, made it possible to reproduce the typical symptoms of the anthracnose of the chickpea. The re-isolation of the pathogen from the diseased seedlings was made easily, who verified the postulate of Koch; we therefore confirm the presence of *Ascochyta rabiei*. Results are shown in Figure 2.

The results obtained on line ILC263 confirm their sensitivity to a large number of isolates. These results were indicated by some authors [14, 8].

After an incubation period of 5 to 6 days with a mean of 5.3, the latency period is between 8 and 9 days with a means of 8.6 days. This difference indicates that the time required for the appearance of the first pycnidia varies from one isolate to another (Table 3).

We also observed that the incubation period varies between 5 and 6 days depending on the isolates, while the latency period lasts from 8 to 9 days. In a similar study of the virulence of six (06) Algerian isolates tested on six (6) differential lineages, [15] found that the incubation period varied between 8 and 9 days, whereas the latency varied between 10 and 13 days. The incubation period variation and the latency period were also indicated (8 to 10) by [9].

In Figure 3 and Figure 4, we note that there are three (03) highly aggressive isolates (REL1, SB2 and MSC2) with categories of severity ranging from 6, 7.5 and 8 respectively. Five (05) isolates are moderately aggressive with categories of severity ranging between 4 to 5.9 (MSC1, SB1, SB3, MOS2 and REL2) and two (02) nonaggressive isolates, with severity levels ranging from 1 to 3.9 (AT1 and MOS1).

$$AI = \frac{1F1 + 2F2 + 3F3 + 4F4 + 5F5 + 6F6 + 7F7 + 8F8 + 9F9}{N} \quad (\text{Eq. 1}) [10].$$

AI: Attack index

F: Number of affected plants for each grade in the rating scales (1-9)

N: Total number of inoculated plants.

FIGURE 2
Severity of the disease on the sensitive line ILC 263

TABLE 3
Incubation and latency periods (in days) of *A. rabiei* isolates.

Isolates	Incubation periods (days)	Latency periods (days)
MSC1	5 ± 0.81	8 ± 0.81
MSC2	5 ± 0.81	9 ± 0.81
AT1	6 ± 0.81	9 ± 0.81
SB1	5 ± 0.81	9 ± 0.81
SB2	5 ± 0.81	8 ± 0.81
SB2	6 ± 0.81	9 ± 0.81
MOS1	5 ± 0.81	9 ± 1.15
MOS2	6 ± 0.81	9 ± 0.81
REL1	5 ± 0.81	8 ± 1.15
REL2	5 ± 0.81	8 ± 0.81
Mean	5.3	8.6

FIGURE 3
Aggressivity of *Ascochyta rabiei* isolates on all lines tested

Significant differences in the degree of severity were found in the isolate, concerning the evaluation of the degree of aggressiveness of our isolates, the results obtained allowed us to note that the isolates (MSC2, SB2 and REL1) are highly aggressive. The isolates (MSC1, SB1, SB3, MOS2 and REL2) are moderately aggressive and the isolates (AT1 and MOS1) are non-aggressive. These results allow us to classify these isolates into three (3) levels of aggressiveness:

highly aggressive isolates, moderately aggressive isolates and non-aggressive isolates. This variability in aggression was also indicated by [16, 17 - 18], [19 - 15] [20 - 8 , 21]. This variability in aggression was also indicated in Indian by [22]. The same study of pathogenic variation of different chickpea lines was obtained in Turkey by [23]. Through the results obtained, we find that the aggressiveness of *A.rabiei* is variable, with highly significant differences between the isolates (Table 4).

FIGURE 4

Average of Aggressivity of *Ascochyta rabiei* isolates

TABLE 4
Aggressiveness of the isolates of *A. rabiei* on 12 chickpea lines

Iso-lates	MSC1	MSC2	AT1	SB1	SB2	SB3	MOS1	MOS2	REL1	REL2	Test F
Mean of aggressiveness	4.12	5.95	2.85	3,35	4,98	4.55	2.55	4,25	5,05	3,25	30.5**
	c.d	A	E	d.e	B	C	F	c.d	B	d,e	

Legend : ** Highly significant effect.

TABLE 5
Reaction of the chickpea lines to *Ascochyta rabiei*

Lines	MSC1	MSC2	AT1	SB1	SB2	SB3	MOS1	MOS2	REL1	REL2
Col 08	7.0	8.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	6.0	8.0	6.0	7.0	6.0
F 97-657	5.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	1.0
ILC 3279	3.0	3.0	3.0	5.0	3.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	5.0
GP 10	7.0	6.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0	8.0	7.0	6.0	6.0
F 03-19C	5.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	3.0
Col 15/24	6.0	8.0	5.0	7.0	8.0	6.0	5.0	8.0	7.0	5.0
Flip 05-69C	4.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	6.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	4.0	5.0
INRA199	7.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	4.0	6.0	6.0
F 10-5/11	6.0	3.0	1.0	6.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
F 482	3.0	5.0	1.0	6.0	5.0	6.0	4.0	3.0	5.0	3.0
ILC 482	7.0	8.0	8.0	6.0	5.0	6.0	4.0	5.0	7.0	6.0
F1025	8.0	6.0	7.0	6.0	7.0	4.0	8.0	6.0	7.0	5.0

ppds F1et F2 = 1,254, ppds F1 x F2 = 4,102 et 6.033 ; C.V= 18.20%.

TABLE 6
Reaction of the chickpea lines after inoculation by 10 isolates of *A.rabiei*

Lines	ILC 482	ILC 3279	INRA 199	Col 25/24	Flip 0569 C	Col 08	GP 10	F 0319C	F 97-657	F 1025	F 482	F Test F 10-5/11
Reaction	5.7 5 A	4.34 Bcd	4.42 Bcd	5.14 Abc	4.55 Cd	4.9 5 C	4.6 2 cd	4.09 D	4.45 Bcd	5.45 Ab	4.2 5 Cd	4.15 d 5.36*

* Significant

TABLE 7
Reaction of the varieties of chickpea with effect the isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei*

Lines	ILC 482	ILC 3279	INRA 199	Col 25/24	Flip 05-69 C	Col 08	GP 10	F 03-19 C	F 97-657	F 1025	F 482	F 10-5/11
MSC1	S	R	S	S	T	S	S	T	T	S	R	T
MSC2	S	R	T	S	T	S	S	T	T	S	T	R
AT1	S	R	T	T	R	S	T	T	T	S	R	R
SB1	S	T	T	S	T	S	S	R	T	S	T	T
SB2	T	R	T	S	T	T	S	R	R	S	T	T
SB3	S	R	T	T	T	T	S	T	T	T	T	R
MOS1	T	T	T	T	R	S	S	T	R	S	T	T
MOS2	T	T	T	S	T	S	S	R	T	S	R	R
REL1	S	R	S	S	T	S	S	T	T	S	T	T
REL2	S	T	S	T	T	T	T	R	R	T	R	T

Legend: Resistant (R) = 1-3.9; Tolerant (T) = 4-5.9; Susceptible (S) = 6-7.9; Very Susceptible (VS) = 8-9 [14].

TABLE 8
Analysis of variance for pathogenicity of *A.rabiei* isolates studied (10 days after inoculation)
(Newman's test Keuls Seuil - 1%).

Source of variation	SSD	^a DF	^b MS	TEST F	PROBA	SD	CV
Isolate	645,124	12	75.01	30,50*	0		
Genotype	756,411	12	112.46	5,36*	0		
Isolate x Genotype	977,122	140	5.33	18.40*	0		
Error	257,145	512	1.25			0.8	18.20%

SSD: Sum of the squares of the deviations; ^aDF: Degrees of freedom; ^bMS: Medium square; SD: Standard deviation; CV: Coefficient of variation; * Significant at 0.01.

Regarding the evaluation of the aggressiveness of the isolates, the analysis of the results showed that the MSC2 isolate is more aggressive (5, 95 a) than all the others, with respect to the inoculated varieties, following the isolate REL1 (5.05 b), and finally isolates AT1 and MOS1 (2.85e and 2.55f) respectively non-aggressive. Isolates MSC1, SB1, SB3, MOS2 and REL2 are moderately aggressive (Groups b, c and d, Table 4). Isolates AT1 and MOS1 are non-aggressive (Groups e and f, Table 4), because the lines inoculated by it expressed resistance. The aggression study revealed three levels: highly aggressive isolates, moderately aggressive isolates and non-aggressive isolates. Similarly, considering the reaction of chickpea strains with respect to isolates of *A.rabiei*, we notice highly significant differences; this reaction varies from one line to another (Table 5 and Table 6). Considering the reaction of the lines to isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei*, we also noticed significant

differences between the lines tested. ILC3279 lines considered resistant in Algeria and other countries [24, 15, 21, 7]. The line ILC482, known to be tolerant, is sensitive to other isolates, these results are in line with those obtained by [14-25] and sensitive to most isolates as described for *A. rabiei* in Syria by [26]. Generally, the reaction of the different lines to isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei* varies between sensitivity, tolerance and resistance. Analysis of the Isolate (F1) x Variety (F2) interaction shows a significant effect (Table 5).

The following table (Table 7) groups the reactions of varieties against all the isolates tested.

The analysis of variance shows that the effects of the pathogen and the isolate as well as their interaction are significant for these parameters (Table 8).

Varieties ILC3279, F482 and F10-5/11 are generally resistant to tolerant for all tested isolates. The

varieties Flip05-69C, F03-19C and F97-657 are tolerant to isolates but resistant to others. Varieties ILC482, Col25/24, Col08, GP10 and F1025 are susceptible to 7 and 8 isolates and are tolerant to others. The INRA199 variety is tolerant to isolates (MSC2, AT1, SB1, SB2, SB3 MOS1 and MOS2), but susceptible to isolates (MSC1, REL1 and REL2). Through the results obtained, we can classify the different lines tested in the following categories:

Category 1: Tolerant to resistant varieties: ILC3279, F 482, F10-5 / 11 and F 03-19 C

Category 2: Varieties tolerant to all isolates: Flip 05-69 C, F97-657 and INRA199

Category 3: Moderately tolerant varieties with isolates: Col 25/24, Col 08 and GP 10

Category 4: Susceptible to moderately tolerant varieties: ILC482 and F 1025.

The study of the pathogenic variability of isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei*, allowed us to find some data to expand and develop knowledge about this fungus. The study of the pathogenicity of the isolates towards a range of different lineages, allowed us to note a significant difference in the aggressiveness of our isolates, as well as a difference in the reaction of the different tested lines, showing the existence of pathogenic variability in all isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei*. The results obtained on line ILC263 confirm their sensitivity to a large number of isolates. These are results indicated by some authors [14, 9]. We also observed that the incubation period varies between 5 and 6 days depending on the isolates, while the latency period lasts from 8 to 9 days [8]. In a similar study of the virulence of six (06) Algerian isolates tested on six (6) differential lineages [26] found that the incubation period varied between 8 and 9 days, whereas the latency varies between 10 and 13 days. Significant differences in the degree of severity were found in the isolate, concerning the evaluation of the degree of aggressiveness of our isolates, the results obtained allowed us to note that the isolates (MSC2, SB2 and REL1) are highly aggressive. The isolates (MSC1, SB1, SB3, MOS2 and REL2) are moderately aggressive and the isolates (AT1 and MOS1) are non-aggressive. These results allow us to classify these isolates into three (3) levels of aggressiveness: highly aggressive isolates, moderately aggressive isolates and non-aggressive isolates. This variability in aggression was also indicated by [16, 17-18 - 15]. [21, 8 -19, 20]. This variability in aggression was also indicated in Indian by [22]. The same study of pathogenic variation of different chickpea lines was obtained in Turkey by [23]. Considering the reaction of the lines to isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei*, we also noticed significant differences between the lines tested. ILC3279 lines considered resistant in Algeria and other countries [24- 15] [21, 7]. The line ILC482, known to be tolerant, is sensitive to other isolates, these results are in line with those obtained by [14, 25] and sensitive to most isolates as described for *A. rabiei* in Syria by [26]. Studies have been carried out

conducted to investigate the effectiveness of *Salvia officinalis* and *Salvia tomentosa* plant essential oils against 6 different isolates of *A. rabiei* pathogen causing significant loss in chickpea production areas [27]. There are several pathogenic diseases have been reported to cause economic losses in chickpea crop in Pakistan. It was also mentioned in the literature that around 50 pathogens of economic significance are affecting the chickpea plant and causing severe diseases [28, 29]. Generally, the reaction of the different lines to isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei* varies between sensitivity, tolerance and resistance.

CONCLUSION

The work we carried out consisted of studying the pathogenicity (aggressiveness and virulence test) of *Ascochyta rabiei* isolates collected in five (05) regions in western Algeria. The study of the pathogenicity made from the interaction of *A. rabiei* isolates with the different (introduced and local) chickpea lines; we found a pathogenic variability between the isolates studied. The results obtained show that the isolates do not attack the lines with the same level of aggressiveness and virulence. These results allowed us to classify our isolates into three (03) levels of aggressiveness: highly aggressive isolates, moderately aggressive isolates and non-aggressive isolates. This ranking shows us that there is a wide spectrum of variability in levels of aggression between isolates. We observed that the isolates (MSC2, SB2 and REL1) are highly aggressive, the isolates (MSC1, SB1, SB3, MOS2 and REL2) are moderately aggressive and the isolates (AT1 and MOS1) non-aggressive. Regarding the reaction of the chickpea strains tested to isolates, shows a variability between isolates studied: resistant to resistant lines (ILC3279, F482, F10-5 / 11 and F03-19C), lines tolerant of all isolates (Flip05-69C, F97-657 and INRA199), moderately tolerant lines (Col25 / 24, Col08 and GP10) and susceptible to tolerant lines (ILC482 and F1025). We have demonstrated that some chickpea lines considered to be resistant to anthracnose are in the case of ILC3279. The results obtained on the line (ILC263) confirm their sensitivity to a large number of isolates. The results obtained on the virulence test allowed us to classify the reaction of the different lines tested with isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei* in three (03) categories: sensitive, tolerant and resistant. From the results obtained it can be said that the thorough knowledge of this pathogen is essential for the choice of any means of control (for example: chemical and biological), it will be necessary to complete this work with another range of introduced lines. And other isolates from different regions of the west and the entire Algerian territory for a more complete characterisation. Through this study, we believe that pathogenic variability is necessary for an approach to molecular characterisation (for example SSR and

RAPD); important condition for obtaining more accurate results. On the other hand, this study should also be completed by comparing the isolates studied with previously identified strains of *A. rabiei*, in order to obtain elements of the answer, as to the identification of the physiological races of *A. rabiei* that exist in Algeria.

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REFERENCES

- [1] MADR. (2014) Statistical Yearbook of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.
- [2] FAO Stat. (2013) Statistical database of the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations.
- [3] Labrousse, F. (1931) Anthracnose of chickpeas. Review of Pathology Vegetal and Entomology Agricultural. 28, 226-231.
- [4] Ahmad, F., Ahmad, I., Aqil, F., Ahmed, W.A. and Sousche, Y.S. (2006) Plant growth promoting blight (*Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Labr.) in chickpeas. Journal of Turkish Phytopathology. 22, 17-26.
- [5] Gan, Y.T., Siddique, K.H.M., Mcleod, W.J. and Jayakumar, P. (2006) Management options for the damage by *Ascochyta* blight (*Ascochyta rabiei*) in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.). Field Crops Res. 97, 121-134.
- [6] Kanouni, H., Taleei, A. and Okhovat, M. (2011) *Ascochyta* blight (*Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Lab.) of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.): Breeding strategies for resistance. International Journal of Plant Breeding and Genetics. 5(1), 1-22.
- [7] Benzohra, I.E., Bendahmane, B.S., Youcef Benkada, M. and Labdi, M. (2015) Screening of 15 chickpea Germplasm accessions for resistance to *Ascochyta rabiei* in North West of Algeria. American-Eurasian Journal of Agricultural & Environmental Science. 15(1), 109-114.
- [8] Benzohra, I.E., Bendahmane, B.S., Labdi, M. and Youcef Benkada, M. (2011) Identification of Pathotypes and Physiological Races in *Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Labr., the agent of *ascochyta* blight in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) in Algeria. World Applied Sciences Journal. 15(7), 978-984.
- [9] INRASBA. (2015) National Institute of Agronomic Research of Sidi Bel Abbes. Algeria. Differential chickpea germ-plasms. World Journal of Agricultural Sciences. 6(5), 630-634.
- [10] Jamil, F.F., Haq, I., Sarwar, N., Alam, S.S., Khan, J.A., Hanif, M., Khan, I.A., Sarwar, M. and Haq, M.A. (2002) Screening of ten advanced chickpea lines for blight and wilt resistance. The Nucleus. 39, 95-100.
- [11] Dolar, F.S., Tenuta, A. and Higgins, V.J. (1994) Detached leaf assay for screening chickpeas for resistance to *Ascochyta* blight. Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology. 16, 215-220.
- [12] Reddy, M.V. and Singh, K.B. (1984) Evaluation of a world collection of chickpea germplasm accessions for resistance to *Ascochyta* blight. Plant Disease. 68, 900-901.
- [13] Türkkkan, M. and Dolar, F.S. (2009) Determination of pathogenic variability of *Didymella rabiei*, the agent of *ascochyta* blight of chickpeas in Turkey. Turkish Journal of Agricultural Forest. 33, 585-591.
- [14] Iqbal, S.M., Ghafoor, A., Ayub, N. and Ahmad, Z. (2004) Pathogenic diversity in *Ascochyta rabiei* isolates collected from Pakistan. Pakistan Journal of Botany. 36(2), 429-437.
- [15] Zikara-Zine, F. and Bouznad, Z. (2007) Virulence and compatibility groups in isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei* in Algeria. INRAA, Algerian National Institute of Agronomic Research. 19, 48-55.
- [16] Jamil, F.F., Sarwar, N., Sarwar, M., Khan, J.A., Geistlinger, J. and Kahl, G. (2000) Genetic and pathogenic diversity within *Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Lab. populations in Pakistan causing blight of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.). Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology. 57, 243-254.
- [17] Chen, W., Coyne, C.J., Peever, T.L. and Muehlbauer, F.J. (2004) Characterization of chickpea differentials for pathogenicity assay of *Ascochyta* blight and identification of chickpea accessions resistant to *Didymella rabiei*. Plant Pathology. 53, 759-769.
- [18] Chongo, G., Gossen, B.D., Bushwaldt, I., Adhikari, T. and Rimmer, S.R. (2004) Genetic diversity of *Ascochyta rabiei* in Canada. Plant Disease. 88, 4-10.
- [19] Jayakumar, P., Gossen, B.D., Gan, Y.T., Banniza, S. and Warkentin, T.D. (2005) *Ascochyta* blight of chickpea: Influence and host resistance mechanisms. Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology. 27, 499-509.
- [20] Ben Mbarek, K. (2011) Behavior of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) of the kabuli type with respect to water stress and identification of drought tolerant genotypes, University of Sousse Chott-Mariem, Tunisia.

- [21] Mahiout, D., Bendahmane, B.S., Youcef Benkada, M. and Martina, R. (2015) Physiological Characterisation of *Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Lab. Isolated from Diseased Chickpea Fields in Six Regions of Northwestern Algeria. American-Eurasian Journal of Agricultural & Environmental Science. 15(6), 1136-1146.
- [22] Basandrai, A.K., Pande, S., Krishna-Kishore, G., Crouch, J.H. and Basandrai, D. (2005) Cultural Morphological and Pathological Variation in Indian Isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei*, the Chickpea Blight Pathogen. Plant Pathology Journal. 21(3), 207-213.
- [23] Ozkilinc, H., Frenkel, O., Shtienberg, D. and Abbo, M. (2011) Aggressiveness of eight *Didymella rabiei* isolates from domesticated and wild chickpea native to Turkey, a case study. Eurasian Journal of Plant Pathology. 131(3), 529-537.
- [24] Labdi, M. (1995) Study of resistance to anthracnose (*Ascochyta rabiei*) in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.). National School of Agricultural Sciences. Montpellier, France.
- [25] Pande, S., Siddique, K.H.M., Kishore, G.K., Bayaa, B., Gaur, P.M., Gowda, C.L.L., Bretag, T.W. and Crouch, J.H. (2005) *Ascochyta* blight of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.): a review of biology, pathogenicity and disease management. Australian Journal of Agricultural Research. 56, 317-332.
- [26] Atik, O., Ahmed, S., Abang, M.M., Imtiyaz, M., Hamwiah, A., Baum, M., El-Ahmed, A., Murad, S. and Yabarak, M.M. (2013) Pathogenic and genetic diversity of *Didymella rabiei* affecting chickpea in Syria. Crop Protection. 46, 70-79.
- [27] Yilar, M. and Bayar, Y. (2019) Antifungal potential of essential oils of *Salvia officinalis* and *Salvia tomentosa* plants on six different isolates of *Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Labr. Fresen. Environ. Bull. 28(3), 2170-2175.
- [28] Jamrol, H.U.R., Khaskhelil, M.I., Maril, J.M. and Rustamani, M.A. (2019) Mycoflora Associated with gram pod borer affected Chickpea. Fresen. Environ. Bull. 28(4), 4054-4071.
- [29] Alkan, M., Erturk, S., Firat, T.A. and Ciftci, E. (2019) Study of insecticidal and behavioral effects and some characteristic of native diatomaceous earth against the bean weevil, *Acanthosclides Obtectus* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). Fresen. Environ. Bull. 28 (5), 2916-2922.

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